

Report:

A4.3.8

Deliverable D7: "Validation report on the extended prediction model for multi-infusions."

This report was written as part of activity 4.3.8 from the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery (MeDD II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2019 and focused on providing traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and mixing behavior and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems. For more details about this project, please visit www.drugmetrology.com

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The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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Introduction to the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery project

The overall aim of this project is to improve dosing accuracy and to enable the traceable measurement of volume, flow and pressure in existing drug delivery devices and in-line sensors operating at very low flow rates. This will be achieved through the development of new calibration methods and by expanding the existing metrological infrastructure. This project will also investigate fast changing flow rates, which are step changes between two flow rates within a second, the physical properties of mixtures of liquids and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems in order to prevent inaccurate measurement results and thus to improve patient safety.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices regarding changes in flow rate, from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids (WP1). For steady flow rates an uncertainty of 1 % ($k=2$) or better is expected, whereas for fast changing flow rates an uncertainty of 2 % ($k=2$) or better is expected. The techniques developed will be used to characterise and validate the different response times of at least 3 different types of drug delivery devices (including infusion analysers) (WP3 and WP4) and one type of flow sensor, to accurately measure the administered flow and volume with the required uncertainties.
2. To upgrade the existing flow facilities and knowledge of the partner NMIs in order to enable the traceable in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids, as a function of the flow rate and pressure difference, with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$). The measurement uncertainty will be validated using Newtonian liquids with traceable dynamic viscosity calibration. Additionally, tests with non-Newtonian liquids will be performed in order to prove the concept. To calibrate transfer standards for the in-line measurement of dynamic viscosity and other physical properties of liquids, in order to use these transfer standards for flow measurement and to determine the mixing behaviour of different liquids.
3. To develop and validate novel calibration procedures for existing medical flow devices (e.g. infusion pumps, pain controllers and infusion pump analysers) with traceability to a primary standard and with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$) for a range of 5 nL/min up to 600 ml/min and also to develop a proof-of-concept on-chip microfluidic pump used as a transfer standard in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min.
4. To design and develop a multi-infusion system containing check valves, with several options for testing how liquids, with different viscosities mix and flow and how this affects drug concentration. The flow rates and pressures will be traceably calibrated in all infusion lines, as well as at the outlet of the syringe pump, to be able to analyse the effects of pressure-equalising devices and to detect occlusion phenomena and bad mixing configurations.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain (i.e. accredited laboratories, instrumentation manufacturers, etc.), standards developing organisations (ISO/TC 30, ISO/TC 48, ISO/TC/SC 62D, ISO/TC 69, ISO/TC 76, ISO/TC 84, ISO/TC 150, ISO/TC 210) and end-users (i.e. hospitals and health centres).

Activity 4.3.8 – Validation report on the extended prediction model for multi-infusions

Overall Objective: Using input from A4.3.1-A4.3.7, NEL, UMCU, METAS and DNV will produce a validation report on the extended prediction model for multi-infusions.

Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator will then submit the validation report to EURAMET as **D7**: ‘Validation report on the extended prediction model for multi-infusions’.

The following Institutes have contributed to this Deliverable:

no	Participant Type	Short Name	Organisation legal full name	Country
5	Internal Funded Partner	METAS	Eidgenössisches Institut für Metrologie METAS	Switzerland
6	Internal Funded Partner	NEL	TÜV SÜD National Engineering Laboratory Limited	United Kingdom
12	External Funded Partner	THL	Technische Hochschule Lübeck	Germany
13	External Funded Partner	UMCU	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht	Netherlands

The progress within this report covers the Period from 1st June 2019 to the end of November 2022.

1 Introduction

Multi-infusion setups are often used in critical care units such as the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) or the Operation Room (OR), where multiple medications are delivered through one single lumen of a thin catheter. The pharmacokinetics of the medications as well as the physical behaviour and effects of the multi-infusion setups are important aspects to understand the delivery of mixtures of several medications. A predictive model for dosing errors including the effect of the length of the catheter, the mechanical compliance of the plastic syringe and the flow inside the lines exhibiting a Poiseuille flow profile has already been reported [1]. This existing model has been extended to include the effect of air bubbles in infusion lines with and without an air filter and the presence of a non-return valve in infusion lines. Several experimental validation measurements have been performed and are described here in this report to validate the extended predictive model for dosing errors of multi-infusion setups.

2 Description of the model

The predictive model for dosing errors in multi-infusion setups has been extensively describe in "Analytical method for calculation of deviations from intended dosages during multi-infusion" [1]. In the following paragraphs (2.1, 2.2, 2.3) we will briefly explain the following effects, respectively : The effect of the composition of the dead volume after the mixing point of the constituent infusions (paragraph 2.1), the compliance and resistance of the infusion setup (paragraph 2.2), the effect of the Poiseuille flow profile on the time-of-arrival of new medication (paragraph 2.3).

Furthermore, the *extended* predictive model includes two new effects:

The effect of air bubbles in infusion lines with and without an air filter [2, 3] (paragraph 2.4), and the presence of a non-return valve in infusion lines [4] (paragraph 2.5)

2.1 Push-out effect

The push-out effect, that results from a change in pump flow rate settings in a multi-infusion set-up, is explained schematically in the Figure 1. In summary : if two different medications, i.e. one critical medication with a low flow (red in Figure 1) and one non-critical medication (blue), are combined in a multi-infusion set-up such as depicted schematically in Figure 1, then an increase in the pump flow rate of the blue medication will result in an unintended (and probably undesired) temporary increase in the partial flow rate of the red medication entering the patient.

In Figure 1, in (a), two infusion pumps are shown, filled with a blue and a red solution, respectively, produce the same flow rate, which is constant in time. The two flows are merged at the mixing point M, and subsequently travel towards point P, which represents the distal tip of the catheter where the fluid enters the blood stream of the patient. Since the flow rates of both pumps are equal, the catheter from point M to point P contains equal amounts of red and blue fluid, in the form of a mixture. This mixture is travelling with a flow rate that is twice the flow rate of each pump. A constant amount r of red fluid is entering the patient during each unit time interval (illustrated by a canister at point P for each unit time interval).

b The same set-up, but now, at $t = 0$, the flow rate of the blue pump is suddenly increased by a factor 5. As a result, after $t = 0$, the amount of red fluid entering the patient at point P now temporarily equals $3r$ per unit time. Therefore, in **b**, the memory effect is visible: the distal part of the catheter (near P) still contains the old mixing ratio corresponding to the situation before $t = 0$. This old mixture is now being pushed out at the new speed; hence we dubbed this temporary increase in output of red fluid the push-out effect. In the literature, this effect is sometimes referred to as dead volume effect, or catheter memory effect. **c** After $t = t_{\text{delay}}$, the amount of red fluid entering the blood stream per unit time equals r again, which equals the intended dose, just like the situation before $t = 0$ in **a**.

Figure 1: Schematic, illustrating the push-out effect, i.e.: the temporary increase in the outflow of the red fluid into the patient due to an increase in speed of the blue pump [1].

2.2 Temporary additional dosing errors due to the combination of Resistance and Mechanical Compliance in the infusion hardware

Modern disposable syringes contain a rubber stopper that is compressible under pressure, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic rendering of the effects of mechanical compressibility (“Compliance”) of various parts of a disposable syringe, such as, notably, the rubber part of the plunger. **Top:** syringe in resting state. **Bottom:** Syringe under pressure, as a result of the pressure exerted by the pump in combination with the resistance of the infusion lines and catheter connected to the syringe. The largest contribution to the mechanical compliance is caused by the compressibility of the rubber stop that sits on top of the plunger.

It has been shown that this compressibility of the plunger gives rise to a delay in the pressure build-up (and hence the build-up of the flow velocity) in the infusion line, and that this delay can be calculated using equivalent electric circuits modelling. For instance, if a new syringe is inserted into the pump, and, subsequently, the pump is started at $t = 0$ with a set flow rate of u_{pump} , then the equivalent circuit method predicts that the actual output flow rate $u_{\text{patient}}(t)$ that enters the bloodstream of the patient at the other end of the catheter, equals :

$$u_{\text{patient}}(t) = u_{\text{pump}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{RC}} \right) \quad (1)$$

in which R is the resistance of the combination of infusion line and catheter, and C is the mechanical compliance (compressibility) of the elastic seal ('stopper') that sits on top of the plunger in the syringe. (Strictly speaking, compression occurs in several elements, such as the elastic stopper, the barrel wall (varying with the position of the stopper), and the compliance of the pump mechanism itself. Therefore, using a single value for C may not always model a given syringe's characteristics completely. For the purpose of explaining the importance of RC -effects in relation to air bubbles and air filters, however, a single C may suffice). The product of R and C is called the RC -time (also referred to as the "time-constant"). It can be seen from equation (1) that only after $t = 3 RC$, i.e. after waiting a time interval that equals three times the RC -time, the flow rate $u_{\text{patient}}(t)$ entering the blood stream of the patient has reached 95% of the intended flow rate u_{pump} . It has been shown [7] that in neonatal care this is of particular clinical relevance, because the resistance R of a catheter is inversely proportional to the diameter of the catheter *to the power four*, which causes very thin catheters (taking a 1 Fr catheter as an extreme example) used in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) to have a remarkably large value of R , and hence a particularly long RC -time of e.g. 105 seconds in case of a 1 French catheter (Vygon Premicath 1-Fr (Ecouen, France)) and a 50 ml syringe (B.Braun Omnifix (B.Braun, Melsungen, Germany)), which entails that it takes over 5 minutes to reach 95% of the set flow rate.

2.3 Effect of Poiseuille Flow Profile on time-of-arrival of new medication after syringe exchange

When a clinician performs a syringe exchange at the infusion pump, he or she is trained to make an estimate of the time delay between the moment that the pump starts pushing the new medication into the infusion system, and the moment that the first 5 % of the new medication has actually entered the bloodstream of the patient after having travelled through the infusion lines and catheter. The clinician will make this estimate based on the *Poiseuille flow profile*: rules of thumb that are valid for the *standard, cylindrically symmetric* tubing that constitutes the combination of infusion line and catheter. One of those rules of thumb is that the first molecules of the new medication will arrive already at *half the time* that would be obtained by simply dividing the internal volume (of the catheter-infusion line combination) by the *flow rate*. This 0.5 factor is based on the fact that, in a Poiseuille flow, at the centerline of the tubing the fluid travels at twice the average velocity of the entire volume.

Figure 3: explaining the effect of the Poiseuille Flow Profile on the time-of-arrival of the (first molecules of) a new medication after a syringe exchange.

In Figure 3, the effect of the Poiseuille Flow Profile on the time-of-arrival of the (first molecules of) a new medication after a syringe exchange is explained schematically. In (a), a longitudinal cross section is depicted schematically. The letter M on the left side denotes the connection of the infusion line to the pump, and, therefore, the start of the build-up of the Poiseuille flow profile. Point P at the right of the schematic denotes the distal end of the catheter, and therefore the entry point into the blood stream of the patient. As can be seen from Figure 3a, the red parabola denotes the very moment that the tip of the Poiseuille profile, containing the new medication after the syringe exchange, had reached the end of the catheter at point P.

Furthermore, in Figure 3b, the fraction of the new medication at a certain position along the length of the catheter is depicted. This fraction has a value between 0 and 1, as depicted on the y-axis of the graph in Figure 3b. As can be seen in Figure 3b, the fraction as function of longitudinal position between points M and P follows a straight line. The red line denotes the same moment in time as the red parabola in Figure 3a.

The essential point now is that, if a syringe exchange has taken place and the pump is restarted at time $t = 0$, then the time t_{first} needed for the first molecules of the new medication to arrive in the blood stream is approximately half the internal volume of the infusion set (V_{internal}) divided by the set flow rate (u_{pump}) of the pump :

$$t_{\text{first}} = \frac{V_{\text{internal}}}{2u_{\text{pump}}}$$

due to the fact that at the very centerline of the infusion line and catheter (i.e., the green dashed line in the Figure 3), the molecules travel at 2 times the average speed (i.e., as averaged over the entire cross-sectional area).

However, there are many factors that can cause deviations from the crude estimate presented in the formula directly above.

For instance, thermal diffusion causes exchange of molecules between the various layers of the Poiseuille flow profile, resulting in the blurring of the parabolic profile and hence an increase in the value of t_{first}

Furthermore, the addition of extra elements into the infusion system, such as a non-return valve, makes it necessary to amend these rules of thumb: Since devices such as a non-return valve may have large internal volumes with respect to the relatively thin infusion lines, there may be a significant extra delay in the time-of-arrival of the first molecules of the new medication in the patient after a syringe exchange.

2.4 The effect of air bubbles in infusion lines with and without an air filter

Air filters have been designed to let air bubbles escape from the infusion line into the environment before these bubbles could enter the patient. In this subsection, we will show the severity of two phenomena that are largely unknown to the medical staff : (i) if air bubbles are removed from the infusion line using an air filter, then an unexpectedly large extra delay in drug delivery may be created owing to pressure effects in combination with compressibility (mechanical compliance) of syringes. Furthermore, (ii) if there is no air filter present, and hence air bubbles are not filtered out, then, after a syringe exchange putting a syringe with a new medication into the pump, the presence of even very small air bubbles may have a profound effect on the time needed for the first molecules of the new medication to arrive at the patient, owing to a distortion of the Poiseuille Flow Profile.

As has been explained in subsection 2.2 above, the combination of resistance R and compliance C of an infusion setup gives rise to a retardation in the build-up of flow when restarting the pump after e.g. a syringe exchange. This retardation is of the order of magnitude of the time constant RC .

The essential point that we address in this subsection 2.4 now is that *this same start-up phenomenon will also occur directly after an air bubble has escaped through an air filter* in the infusion set-up: an air filter in an infusion line is equipped with microscopic orifices that allows air to escape into the environment, but keeps liquids inside (called 'hydrophobic' filters). If an air bubble is present inside the infusion line near the pump, it will travel along with the fluid through the infusion line, until it reaches the air filter. Once the air bubble enters the air filter, the air escapes immediately to the environment, giving rise to a *sudden pressure drop* in the part of the infusion line between the pump and the air filter, which on its turn causes the compressible part of the plunger (called the plunger stopper) of the syringe to relax into its original unpressurized state. As a result, the actual flow rate of the fluid entering the bloodstream of the patient drops as well, and needs time to be restored. This is phenomenon (i) mentioned above at the beginning of subsection 2.4.

Furthermore, in the case that an air bubble is present inside an infusion system that does *not* incorporate an air filter, a different mechanism can still take place (phenomenon (ii)) : Any tiny air bubble that is still large enough to cover the whole cross-sectional area of a (thin) catheter or infusion line will prevent the development of a complete Poiseuille flow profile throughout the catheter or infusion line (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: *Photographical illustration of the effect of an air bubble in an infusion line. a) Medication from a new syringe (blue dye in this photograph), entering the infusion line directly after a syringe exchange, is trapped behind an air bubble. The direction of the flow is from left to right in this picture. Length of the air bubble is about 1 cm. Distance between grid lines on the paper in the background is 5 mm. The “old” medication (transparent, without dye), pumped into the infusion line before the syringe exchange, is still present inside the infusion line directly next to the air bubble at the right side of the bubble. Flow rate was 20 ml/h. b) As in (a), but now without air bubble, allowing a Poiseuille flow profile to develop. c) As in (b), still without air bubble, but now after a longer period of time, and farther from the entrance of the infusion line, showing further development of the Poiseuille flow profile.*

2.5 Effect of non-return valves on the time-of-arrival of new medication in a patient after syringe exchange

It has been known for many decades now that when a patient is connected to an infusion line, the risks of fluids travelling in the opposite direction (i.e., going away from the patient instead of going towards the patient) should be mitigated. To this end, many infusion sets are equipped with a non-return valve (also referred to as one-way valve, anti-reflux valve, or check valve, see Figure 5 for an example) that makes it impossible for fluids to travel in the wrong direction. Evidently, the internal mechanisms inside such a non-return valve will involve structures that are not present in the standard infusion lines themselves, and may deviate substantially from the cylindrically symmetric nature of the inner lumina of infusion lines and catheters.

Therefore, the presence of a non-return valve in an infusion set-up is expected to affect the time-of-arrival of new medication in a patient after syringe exchange. Using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) we have studied the flow through a typical non-return valve, focusing on two separate effects: (A) the overall delay in the time-of-arrival, and (B) timing effects due to the distortion of the Poiseuille flow profile in the non-return valve. The results show that (A) the additional delay in time-of-arrival of new medication, caused by the non-return valve alone, corresponds to the delay that would be caused by 11.2 cm of extra infusion line instead of the valve, and that (B) the non-Poiseuille flow profile inside the non-return valve gives rise to an extra slow wash-out of the last

portion of the remnant fluid of the old medication. We conclude that awareness of these extra delays may be important for clinicians in certain time-critical situations.

Figure 5: Photograph (close-up) of a clinically-used non-return valve employed in this study. The dark, slit-like, narrow opening visible in the red rubber structure corresponds to an opening angle of approximately 1 degree, between the moveable, hinged part (flap) of the red rubber and the fixed part. The hinge itself, connecting the moveable part of the red rubber to the fixed part is located at the other side and hence not visible in this photo.

3 Validation procedure The extended predictive model needed to be validated with various experiments, where parts of the multi-infusion lines are investigated in isolated experiments and in a representative multi-infusion setup of clinical care. Single effects are easier to reproduce and compare the experimental results with the predictive model. It is important to show the qualitative accuracy of the prediction of the different flow behaviour in the different infusion lines depending on the components and the flow rate changes of the multi-infusion setups. In clinical application the pharmacokinetics play an important role and are therefore as important as the physical effects described in this validation report. Therefore, sometimes the phenomenological effects of the infusion setup are more important than the quantitative description and calculation of a realistic clinical multi-infusion setup. Metrologists can specify and ensure stable lab conditions for the characterisation of multi-infusion setups, but the real-life setup under examination is not so well-characterised and at times also very dynamic.

For each component of the multi-infusion setup the flow resistance, the mechanical compliance and the internal volume have to be determined or estimated. These parameters will be implemented in the calculations of the extended predictive model and flow curves will be compared to the experimental measurements. Therefore, the different effects listed in chapter 4 were investigated.

4 Measurements & Validation of model components In this section, we present the results of in-vitro measurements in order to validate the various components in the theoretical model described in section 2. The first three subsection (4.1, 4.2, 4.3) will represent the three components (a), (b), and (c) from the theoretical curves in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Sketch of key characteristics of a dosing error distribution. **a** Push-out effect before the tip of Poiseuille profile has reached the patient. **b** Decaying remnant tail of push-out effect, due to Poiseuille mixing. **c** Dosing error due to mechanical compliances.

4.1 Component 1 Push out effect before tip of Poiseuille profile of new mixture reaches patient

The push-out effect is visible in the boxes (A) and (C) in Figure 5. Despite the fact that, at $t=20$ minutes, only the pump flow rate of the syringe containing the pure water is changed (dotted black line in Figure 5), the partial flow rate of the red solution entering the (virtual) patient apparently changes as well, in spite of the fact that the pump flow rate of the red solution has not been altered. This is called the push-out effect.

The theoretical dosing error in the red solution entering the patient equals (see eq. (8) in [1]) reads :

$$20 < t < 20 + \frac{V_{internal}}{2u_{pump}} : \quad DosingErrorInRED = u_{RED} \frac{u_{pumpWaterHigh} - u_{pumpWaterLow}}{u_{pumpWaterLow} + u_{RED}}$$

Which, in the case of the set-up of Figure 5, yields the theoretical value:

Theoretical dosing error in RED at (A): $DosingErrorInRED = 6.7 \text{ ml/h}$

Likewise, the same formula yields the opposite value for the dosing error during episode (C) :

Theoretical dosing error in RED at (A): $DosingErrorInRED = - 6.7 \text{ ml/h}$

Due to the fact that the Total flow rate (Green line in Figure 5) does follow the sum of the pump set flow rates (dotted grey line plus dotted red line) correctly, it follows that during period (A) the measured partial flow rate of the Water (continuous black line) is too small with respect to its pump set flow rate (i.e., the dotted black line); this discrepancy is also equal to :

Theoretical dosing error in BLACK at (A): - 6.7 ml/h

Theoretical dosing error in BLACK at (C): 6.7 ml/h

Figure 5: Results from an in-vitro experiment in a multi-infusion set-up, with two syringes: one filled with a red dye solution, and the other with pure water. At $t=20$ minutes, the flow rate of the syringe containing the pure water is increased, and at $t=65$ minutes this flow rate is restored to its original value again. Data from experiments at NEL.

4.2 Component 2 Push out effect (Remnant tail) after tip of Poiseuille profile of new mixture reaches patient

In this subsection, we focus on the episodes (B) and (D) in Figure 5, which are the episodes during which the “remnant tail” of the Push-out effect becomes apparent. This “remnant tail” results from the combination of the Poiseuille profile with the push-out effect, and corresponds to the theoretical Figure 4b, and has the following formula, as explained in [1] :

For $t > 20 + \frac{V_{\text{internal}}}{2u_{\text{pump}}}$:

$$\text{DosingErrorInRED}(t) = u_{\text{RED}} \frac{(u_{\text{pumpWaterHigh}} - u_{\text{pumpWaterLow}})V_{\text{internal}}}{(u_{\text{pumpWaterLow}} + u_{\text{RED}})(V_{\text{internal}} + 2\tau(u_{\text{pumpWaterHigh}} + u_{\text{RED}}))}$$

As can be seen from the formula directly above, the time dependency appears in the denominator as τ in which $\tau = t - 20 + \frac{V_{\text{internal}}}{2u_{\text{pump}}}$

This implies that if the Dosing Error is inverted, i.e. if $1 / \text{DosingErrorInRED}(t)$ would be plotted as function of τ , then a linear relation would appear :

$$1 / \text{DosingErrorInRED}(t) = \frac{(u_{\text{pumpWaterLow}} + u_{\text{RED}})(V_{\text{internal}} + 2\tau(u_{\text{pumpWaterHigh}} + u_{\text{RED}}))}{u_{\text{RED}}(u_{\text{pumpWaterHigh}} - u_{\text{pumpWaterLow}})V_{\text{internal}}}$$

Let the formula directly above be referred to as the “linear testing formula”.

In the following graphs, we first show the $\text{DosingErrorInRED}(t)$ as well as the $\text{DosingErrorInWATER}(t)$ for both periods (B) and (D).

Subsequently, we will apply the linear testing formula (see above) on both intervals (B) and (D).

Figure 6: Dosing errors in Water and in Red solution, showing the “remnant tail” phenomenon during episode (B), in which $\text{Water}(0)$ and $\text{Red}(0)$ refer to the stationary values reached directly after episode (B).

Figure 7: Dosing errors in Water and in Red solution, showing the “remnant tail” phenomenon during episode (D)

In the following, we now apply the “linear testing formula” as described above, and perform Linear Regression Analysis to quantify the correspondence between theory and measurement.

Starting with episode (B), we have Figure 8 directly below :

Figure 8: $1/\text{DosingErrorInWATER}$ as function of time τ , showing a quasi-linear relationship during episode (B)

Figure 9: $1/\text{DosingErrorInWATER}$ as function of time τ , showing a quasi-linear relationship during episode (D)

We conclude that for both episodes (B) and (D), the linear Pearson’s R of the Linear Regression of $1/\text{DosingErrorInWATER}$ shows reasonable values, which makes it consistent with the formula for the remnant tail of the Dosing Errors shown above in subsection 4.2.

4.3 Compliance and Resistance

4.3.1 Flow resistance Pa/(mL/h)

The flow resistance is determined by measuring the pressure drop of the component as a function of flow rate. The experimental setup consists of pressure sensors upstream and downstream of the component. The pressure drop of the connectors has also to be measured in order to calculate the pressure drop of the component alone as a function of flow rate. A linear fit is applied and the slope gives the flow resistance in the unit Pa/(mL/h). For the check valve and the anti-siphon valve a start-up pressure for opening the valve is expected, which corresponds to the intercept of the linear fit in the unit Pa.

Table 1: flow resistance of commonly used components in multi infusion setups

component	type	Flow resistance (Pa/(mL/h))	Start up pressure for opening (Pa)	Internal volume (micro L)
Check valve	NRV from IV Slotset Neo	987 ± 50	-	-
Anti Siphon Valve	BD Ref 04302260452	150 ± 50	14000 ± 1000	200
Central catheter	Various types	7 - 200	n/a	-
Umbilical catheter	VYCON Ref 1270.04 4 Fr (ID 0.8 mm, OD 1.5 mm, L 40 cm)	10 ± 1	n/a	360
Infusion line	BD Ref G40020B (L 200 cm, vol 1.4 mL)	33.3 ± 1.7	n/a	1400
Infusion line	VYCON Ref 71100.20 (ID 1 mm, OD 2 mm, L 200 cm, vol 2.0 mL)	16.0 ± 0.8	n/a	2000
Air filter	Pall Medical Filter Ref NEO96E (0.2 micro, vol 0.4 mL)	78.0 ± 4.0	n/a	400
Flow sensor	LD20-600L, Sensirion AG	1.05 ± 0.05	n/a	10
Flow sensor	Coriflow M12, Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V.	1000 ± 50	n/a	-
Pressure sensor	MERIT MSS-005G-001	0.050 ± 0.005	n/a	400
Density and viscosity sensor	Truedyne VLO-M1	2.0 ± 0.1	n/a	-
Density and viscosity sensor	Conventional Viscosity Measurement System of BHT	1700 ± 60	n/a	> 400

The large flow resistance leads to an important RC time of the system, which will cause large start-up times and strong effects in the multi-infusion setup. Sensors that are implemented to characterize the physical effects of the multi-infusion systems should not have large flow resistance, because additional large flow resistance will influence the physical effects on the setup. The flow resistance

of the implemented sensors should be much smaller than the one of the components in order to be negligible with respect to the RC-times.

4.3.2 Mechanical Compliance mL/Pa

The mechanical compliance of a component is determined by measuring the decay time of the flow rate, when the generation of flow is stopped. The decay time RC allows the calculation of the mechanical compliance C with the known flow resistance R of the component. Infusion lines and catheter were connected to the piston prover, which has a mechanical compliance that is negligible as the piston is made of glass. The decay time of the flow rate is due to the flow resistance and the mechanical compliance of the component.

The logarithm of the flow rate as a function of time shows a linear part and the slope corresponds to the inverse of the decay time.

Table 2: RC-times and mechanical compliance of commonly used components in multi infusion setups

component	type	Flow resistance (Pa/(mL/h))	RC-time (s)	Compliance (mL/Pa)
Check valve	NRV from IV Slotset Neo	987 ± 50	-	0
Umbilical catheter	VYCON Ref 1270.04 4 Fr (ID 0.8 mm, OD 1.5 mm, L 40 cm)	10 ± 1	0.165 ± 0.010	(0.46 ± 0.02) · 10 ⁻⁵
Flow sensor	Sensirion LD20-600L	1.05 ± 0.05	n/a	n/a, stiff
Flow sensor	Coriflow M12, Bronkhorst High-Tech B.V.	1000 ± 50	n/a	n/a, stiff
Pressure sensor	MERIT MSS-005G-001	0.050 ± 0.005	n/a	n/a, stiff
Infusion line	BD Ref G40020B (L 200 cm, vol 1.4 mL)	33.3 ± 1.7	0.207 ± 0.010	(0.17 ± 0.01) · 10 ⁻⁵
Infusion line	VYCON Ref 71100.20 (ID 1 mm, OD 2 mm, L 200 cm, vol 2.0 mL)	16.0 ± 0.8	0.214 ± 0.010	(0.37 ± 0.02) · 10 ⁻⁵
Air filter	Pall Medical Filter Ref NEO96E (0.2 micro, vol 0.4 mL)	78.0 ± 4.0	n/a	-
Combination of infusion lines and filter	BD Ref G40020B & Pall Medical Filter Ref NEO96E & BD Ref G40020B	145 ± 8	0.592	(0.11 ± 0.01) · 10 ⁻⁵
Clinical syringe pump	BD Alaris syringe pump with the mounted BD Plastipak 50	n/a	n/a	(1.8 ± 0.2) · 10 ⁻⁵

4.3.3 Elementary testing of the RC times in an in-vitro set-up.

The in-vitro set-up used to test the RC values has been described in [3].

During the first episode (a), as indicated in the Figure 10, the exponential decrease of the dosing error is visible directly after starting the pump. Subsequently, during episode (b), the steady state situation has been reached.

Figure 10: Effects of Mechanical Compliance in an in-vitro set-up directly after starting the pump. See Table directly below for the characteristics of this in-vitro set-up, including the theoretically estimated RC-times. Directly following this Table, another table is presented showing the RC-times as distilled from the experimental results shown in this graph.

Table 3: Resistance and Compressibility values of components in the in-vitro set-up, to be used for the numerical modelling

symbol	component	value	unit
R_{before}	Infusion line	23.6	Pa . h / ml
$R_{\text{before}} + R_{\text{after}}$	Flow meter + Infusion line	1145	Pa . h / ml
C	Syringe (50 ml)	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	ml / Pa
$R_{\text{before}}C$	RC-time	1.27	s
$(R_{\text{before}} + R_{\text{after}})C$	RC-time	61.8	s

Table 4: RC-times for various bubble lengths

Bubble length (cm)	RC time (s) at situation (a)
5.5	57
8.6	60
10.3	51

4.4 Check Valve

The presence of a non-return valve in an infusion set-up is expected to affect the time-of arrival of new medication in a patient after syringe exchange. Using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) we have studied the flow through a typical non-return valve, focusing on two separate effects: (A) the overall delay in the time-of-arrival, and (B) timing effects due to the distortion of the Poiseuille flow profile in the non-return valve. The results show that (A) the additional delay in time-of-arrival of new medication, caused by the non-return valve alone, corresponds to the delay that would be caused by 11.2 cm of extra infusion line instead of the valve, and that (B) the non-Poiseuille flow profile inside the non-return valve gives rise to an extra slow wash-out of the last portion of the remnant fluid of the old medication (see Figure 11)[4].

Figure 11: The presence of a non-return valve in an infusion set causes an additional delay in time-of-arrival of new medication and the non-Poiseuille flow profile inside the non-return valve gives rise to an extra slow wash-out of the last portion of the remnant fluid of the old medication.

4.5 Air bubble in the infusion line with air filter

Any air bubble that is large enough to cover the whole cross-sectional area of an infusion line, will travel through the infusion line along with the fluid, i.e. the velocity of the air bubble equals the average speed inside the infusion line (commonly referred to as 'plug flow'). As a result, the air bubble behaves just like the rest of the infusion line, except near the location of the air filter. For the liquid in the infusion system, the air filter behaves like a normal piece of infusion line. If an air bubble arrives at the location of the air filter, however, the air filter functions as a temporary shortcut to the environment for the duration of the air escaping through the filter. Once the entire air bubble has escaped to the environment, the air filter behaves like a normal piece of infusion line again [3]. The result of the numerical modeling of the phenomenon, where an air bubble is removed from the infusion line using an air filter is shown in Figure 12. All input parameters for the model match the resistance and the mechanical compliance of the components used in the measurement setup (Figure 13) of the results shown in Figure 14. The results of the in-vitro experiment and the extended predictive model show consistent behavior in the drop down and the increase in flow rate, when the air bubble arrives at the air filter and the air escapes from the infusion line.

Figure 12: The result of the numerical modeling of phenomenon, where an air bubble is removed from the infusion line using an air filter [3].

Figure 13: Simplification of the NICU infusion set containing an air filter. Adapted from Snijder et al [5].

Figure 14: Output flow rates, as measured by the flow meter at the end of the infusion line (see Figure 13), during passage of air bubbles of various sizes through the air filter. (a) initial start-up time of flow, (b) steady flow, (c) drop in flow when the air bubble escapes through the air filter, (d) increase in flow after air bubble escaped through the air filter, (e) steady flow without air bubble in infusion line.

The RC-times in the increase of flow with the air bubble in the infusion line (a) are always larger than the RC-times without the air bubble in the infusion line (d), which demonstrates that the compliance of the air bubble plays also its role in the physical effect [3].

METAS performed the same experiments with an BD Alaris GH Guardrails syringe pump, a BD Plastipak 50 syringe, an BD infusion line (Ref G40020B, 200 cm, 1.4 mL) before and after the Pall Medical Filter (Ref NEO96E, 0.2 micro, 0.4 mL) and an umbilical catheter (VYCON Ref 1270.04, 4 Fr, ID 0.8 mm, OD 1.5 mm, L 40 cm). The flow rate has been determined with the gravimetric method.

It turned out that for short length of air bubbles between 5 cm and 10 cm the above described effect did not show up. This means that the Luer Lock connectors in the setup contained probably still some air bubbles after flushing the setup, where additional air bubbles could be collected and no obvious effect of the air filter has been recorded. As no colorants were used for the water, the detection of such air bubbles turned out to be extremely difficult. Nevertheless, the effect of the drop down and increase in flow rate was observed when air bubbles of length of the order of 30 cm or 50 cm were introduced in the infusion line (see Figure 15). Obviously, such long air bubbles are not common in clinical practice.

Figure 15: Effect of large air bubble escape through the air filter in the infusion line. (blue) BD Alaris GH Guardrails syringe pump with BD Plastipak 50 syringe and (red) METAS Piston (zero compliance). Both setups with the same infusion line composed of an BD infusion line (Ref G40020B, 200 cm, 1.4 mL) before and after the Pall Medical Filter (Ref NEO96E, 0.2 micro, 0.4 mL) and an umbilical catheter (VYCON Ref 1270.04, 4 Fr, ID 0.8 mm, OD 1.5 mm, L 40 cm).

The following RC-times were observed for these measurements (see Table 5). The first start-up time with the large air bubble in the infusion line is larger than the start-up time without air bubble, where the compliance of the air bubble plays an important role. Assuming that the BD Alaris syringe pump with the mounted BD Plastipak 50 does not have an flow resistance (values not known, but certainly not true), the calculated compliance of the infusion setup is $2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$. This is a qualitative reasonable value as for an 50 mL plastic syringe usually compliance values of $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ are applied, which is the largest contribution of compliance to the infusion setup.

In order to investigate the influence of the BD Alaris syringe pump with the mounted BD Plastipak 50, the same measurements have been performed by replacing the BD Alaris syringe pump with the METAS Piston Prover, where the compliance is assumed to be zero (glass syringe with PTFE plunger). The compliance of the infusion setup reduces to $0.16 \cdot 10^{-5}$, which is $1.84 \cdot 10^{-5}$ smaller than the infusion setup with BD Alaris syringe pump with the mounted BD Plastipak 50. Therefore, the

compliance of the BD Alaris syringe pump with the mounted BD Plastipak 50 can be estimated to be $1.84 \cdot 10^{-5}$, which is at least ten times larger than the composed infusion line.

Note that the negative flow rate in Figure 15, when the air bubble is escaping the infusion line through the air filter and the pressure is reduced in the infusion line, has not been further investigated. The reasons might be that the gravimetric setup was slightly higher than the infusion line causing backflow due to the reduced pressure.

Table 5: RC-times for the different infusion setups investigating the effect of the air bubble in the infusion line.

Infusion Setup	Effect	RC-time (s)	Resistance of infusion setup (Pa/(mL/h))	Compliance (mL/Pa)
BD Alaris & components (see text) & 50 cm air bubble	Start-up	22.8	155	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
BD Alaris & components (see text) & 50 cm air bubble	2 nd start-up and final decay	10.9	155	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$
METAS Piston Prover & components (see text) & 36 cm air bubble	Start-up	1.55	155	$0.28 \cdot 10^{-5}$
METAS Piston Prover & components (see text) & 36 cm air bubble	2 nd start-up and final decay	0.90	155	$0.16 \cdot 10^{-5}$

5 Visualization Software

Besides being aware and vigilant concerning these counter-intuitive net effects of the combination of push-out and mechanical compliance effects in multi-infusion, physicians may use a bed-side predictions tool (small computer attached to the multi-infusion set-up) that provides insight into the dosing errors that are to be expected after syringe exchange or changes in pump flow rate settings. Such a bed-side prediction tool is currently in development (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: The predictive tool to present the results of the extended predictive model.

In Figure 16, top-left the two-pump system is described. In this example, the set flowrate of pump A is changed. In 'Materials' the syringes and mixing points that are used can be selected from the drop-down menus. The impact of changing the set flowrate on pump A on the resulting flow of the substance in pump B at the vascular access point is presented in the different graphs. In the top-right the total dosing errors is shown. The bottom-left graph shows the set flow rate (yellow) and the actual flow rate (purple) of the critical medication from pump B. The bottom-right graph shows the contribution of different factors to the deviation from the set flow rate of pump B.

6 Measurements not performed

The activity A4.3.7 describes the measurements to be performed in order to fully validate the extended predictive model and the prototype pressure-equalising device (from UMCU).

The prototype pressure-equalising device from UMCU was leaking. Another prototype manifold device from a manufacturer was not fabricated with luer lock connectors. Therefore, it could not be validated.

7 Conclusion

The extended predictive model for dosing errors in multi-infusion setups has been described in this report including the following effects:

- the effect of the composition of the dead volume after the mixing point of the constituent infusions
- the compliance and resistance of the infusion setup
- the effect of the Poiseuille flow profile on the time-of-arrival of new medication
- the effect of air bubbles in infusion lines with and without an air filter
- the presence of a non-return valve in infusion lines.

Various experiments, where parts of the multi-infusion lines are investigated in isolated experiments or in a representative multi-infusion setup of clinical care, have been performed to validate the extended predictive model.

In clinical application the pharmacokinetics play an important role and are therefore as important as the physical effects described in this validation report. Therefore, sometimes the phenomenological effects of the infusion setup are more important than the quantitative description and calculation of a realistic clinical multi-infusion setup.

Nevertheless, it is important to point out that the quantitative effects of the extended predictive model are in clinically excellent agreement with the experiments performed in the laboratory. Qualitatively, the various effects are perfectly described by the extended predictive model. Obviously, such detailed investigations are possible in preclinical work or R&D activities, but the reality of clinical practice is not reproducible in the laboratory.

The visualization software is a valuable predictive tool to show the different effects influencing the delivered medication to the patients. It can be used as a bedside prediction tool in clinical environments, in workshops or e-learning courses to demonstrate the different physical phenomena in multi-infusion systems.

8 References

- [1] Konings M.K., Snijder R.A., Radermacher J.H. and Timmerman A.M. Analytical method for calculation of deviations from intended dosages during multi-infusion. *Biomed OnLine* (2017) 16:18
- [2] Haaijer K. Modelling multi-infusion: the effects of flow rate changes and air on drug administration, Master Thesis, Technical University of Eindhoven, Eindhoven, May 30 2020
- [3] Konings M.K., Haaijer K., Gevers R. and Timmerman A.M. Unexpected dosing errors due to air bubbles in infusion lines with and without air filters. *In press*. *Biomed Eng* 2022.
- [4] Konings M.K., Gevers R., Meijri S. and Timmerman A.M. Effect of non-return valves on the time-of-arrival of new medication in a patient after syringe exchange in an infusion set-up. *In press*. *Biomed Eng* 2022.
- [5] Snijder RA, Konings MK, Van den Hoogen A, Timmerman AM, Impact of Physical Parameters on Dosing Errors due to a Syringe Exchange in Multi-Infusion Therapy. *Pharmaceutical Technology in Hospital Pharmacy*, vol. 2, may 2017.